

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives. Part IX¹: Synthesis of Pyrano (3,2-c) Quinolines

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2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (I), on Perkin reaction with acetyl glycine, acetic anhydride and triethylamine gave 3-acetamido-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline derivatives (IIa) which on hydrolysis with dil. H_2SO_4 (50%) gave 3-hydroxy-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline derivatives (IIb). (I), on Knoevenagel condensation with diethyl malonate, ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl cyanoacetate, gave (III a), (III b) and (III c) respectively.

IN continuation of our work on the synthesis of pyrano quinolines¹, we report here the synthesis of 2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline derivatives. 2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy quinoline derivatives (I) on Perkin reaction with acetyl glycine, acetic anhydride and triethylamine gave 3-acetamido-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline (II a). I. R. spectrum of (II a) showed stretching bands at 1740 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group) and 1640 cm^{-1} (amide $>C=O$ group). (II a), on hydrolysis with dilute H_2SO_4 (50%) in ethyl alcohol in nitrogen atmosphere gave 3-hydroxy-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline (II b). (II b) developed a green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution which is characteristic of 3-hydroxy coumarin derivatives. I. R. spectrum of (II b) showed bands at 3300 cm^{-1} (broad, OH group) and 1730 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group).

- (Ia) R=H
- (Ib) R=8-Me
- (Ic) R=6-Me
- (Id) R=6-MeO
- (Ie) R=6-EtO

- (IIa) R=H, R₁=-NH-C(=O)-CH₃
- (IIb) R=H, R₁=-OH
- (IIc) R=H, R₁=-CO-CH₃

2, 8-Dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline, 2, 6-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy quinoline, 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy-6-methoxy quinoline and 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy-6-ethoxy quinoline on similar series of reactions gave the corresponding 3-hydroxy-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline derivatives.

- (IIIa) R=H, R₁=-COCH₃
- (IIIb) R=H, R₁=-COOC₂H₅
- (IIIc) R=H, R₁=-CN

(I), on Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of pyridine-piperidine mixture, gave a novel compound 3-acetyl-4-(N-piperidyl)-3, 4-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline (III a) and not the normal product (II c). The I. R. spectrum of (III a) showed bands at 1730 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group), 1640 cm^{-1} ($-COCH_3$ group). The structure of (III a) was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CF_3COOH): δ ; 1.88, broad singlet, 6H, $-CH_2-$ group at C_{3'}, 4', 5' of piperidine; 2.25, singlet, 3H, $-CH_3$ group at C₅; 3.33, broad singlet, 4H, $-CH_2-$ group at C_{2'}, 6' of piperidine; 3.7, doublet, J=6Hz, 1H at C₄; 4.1 doublet, J=6Hz, 1H at C₃ and 8.1-8.6, multiplet, 4H, aromatic. The structure of (III a) was further supported by mass-spectrum which did not show the molecular ion peak, but the following peaks were prominent; m/e; 254, (M-piperidyl group), 226, (M \pm piperidyl-CO group), 84, (C₅H₁₀N⁺).

When (I), was condensed with diethyl malonate as above, it gave 3-carbethoxy-4-(N-piperidyl)-3, 4-dihydro-

5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline (III b). The structure of (III b) was confirmed by its IR and NMR spectra. The IR spectrum of (III b) showed bands at 1700 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group) and 1640 cm^{-1} for $>C=O$ of carbethoxy group. The NMR (CF_3COOH) showed signals at δ ; 1.55, triplet, $J=8\text{ Hz}$, $3\text{H}-\text{CH}_3$ group of ester; 1.80, (broad singlet, 6H , $-\text{CH}_2$ -groups $\text{C}_{3'}$, $4'$, $5'$ of piperidine; 2.25, singlet, 3H , $-\text{CH}_3$ group at C_5 , 3.65, doublet, $J=6\text{ Hz}$, 1H at C_4 ; 4.00, doublet $J=6\text{ Hz}$, 1H at C_8 , 3.35, broad singlet, 4H , $-\text{CH}_2$ -group at $\text{C}_{2'}$, $6'$ of piperidine; 4.6 quartet, $J=8\text{ Hz}$, 2H , $-\text{CH}_2$ -group of ester and 8.2–8.8 multiplet, 4H , aromatic.

(I), on similar condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate gave, 3-cyano-4-(N-piperidyl)-3, 4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline (III c).

It appears that (I) on Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl acetoacetate first forms 3-acetyl-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline, (II c), which reacts further to undergo Michael condensation with piperidine to give (III b).

Experimental

3-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline :

A mixture of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy quinoline (1.0 g) acetyl glycine (1.2 g), acetic anhydride (10.0 ml) and triethylamine (4.0 gm) was refluxed on an oil bath at 110° for 20 hrs. The reaction mixture

was then poured into water and separated product was filtered and then crystallized from acetic acid; yield (2.0 gm) m. p. 298° (Found C, 67.05; H, 4.35; N, 9.997; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$; requires C, 67.18; H, 4.48; N, 10.45%). The above product (1.0 g) was heated with 50% dilute H_2SO_4 and ethyl alcohol (1:1) mixture (40 ml) in an inert atmosphere of N_2 gas for 5-6 hrs. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and neutralised with 10% Na_2CO_3 solution, to give free base. The separated product was filtered and washed with water. It crystallised from alcohol, yield 0.6 gm. The m. p.s and analytical data of compounds thus prepared are reported in Table 1.

3-Carbethoxy-4-(N-piperidyl)-5-methyl-3, 4-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline :

2-Methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy quinoline (1.0 g) was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml.) and was refluxed with diethylmalonate (1.0 ml) in the presence of few drops of piperidine on steam bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was then left overnight at room temperature. The product obtained was filtered and washed with petroleum ether to remove unreacted compounds. The product crystallised from ethanol, yield 1.0 gm, m. p. 220° (d). (Found C, 68.68; H, 6.549; N, 7.39; $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$; requires C, 68.50; H, 6.523; N, 7.61%)^a

The m. p.s and analytical data of these compounds prepared by condensation of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxy quinoline derivatives, with ethylacetoacetate and ethyl cyano acetate are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 1—5-METHYL-2-OXO-2H-PYRANO (3,2-C) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R_1	M.P. $^\circ\text{C}$	Found			Molecular formula	Required		
			C%	H%	N%		C%	H%	N%
H	NHCOCH_3	298	67.05	4.53	9.99	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	67.18	4.48	10.45
H	OH	251	68.56	4.12	6.08	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$	68.70	3.96	6.17
7-methyl	NHCOCH_3	307	68.36	4.65	9.62	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	68.10	4.96	9.93
7-methyl	OH	274	69.26	4.48	5.48	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$	69.72	4.56	5.81
9-methyl	NHCOCH_3	311	68.00	4.58	9.95	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	68.10	4.96	9.93
9-methyl	OH	320	69.57	4.80	5.73	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$	69.72	4.56	5.81
9-ethoxy	NHCOCH_3	272	64.97	5.16	8.83	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	65.38	5.12	8.97
9-ethoxy	OH	242	66.63	4.45	4.85	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4$	66.42	4.79	5.16
9-methoxy	NHCOCH_3	275	63.98	4.58	8.93	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	64.43	4.69	9.40
9-methoxy	OH	221	65.67	4.47	5.85	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4$	65.38	4.28	5.44

TABLE 2-4. (N-PIPERIDYL)-5-METHYL-3,4-DIHYDRO-2-OXO-2H PYRANO (3,2-C) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Found			Molecular formula	Required		
			C%	H%	N%		C%	H%	N%
H	-COOC ₂ H ₅	220 (dec.)	68.68	6.54	7.39	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	68.50	6.52	7.61
H	-COCH ₃	192 (dec.)	71.37	6.27	8.21	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	71.00	6.51	8.28
H	-CN	156 (dec.)	70.52	6.01	12.58	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	71.02	5.92	13.08
9-methyl	-COOC ₂ H ₅	243	69.21	6.62	7.80	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	69.10	6.80	7.33
9-methyl	-COCH ₃	220 (dec.)	72.08	6.43	8.00	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	71.60	6.82	8.07
9-methyl	-CN	278 (dec.)	71.99	6.69	12.05	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	71.65	6.27	12.54
7-methyl	-COOC ₂ H ₅	213	68.96	6.75	7.45	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	69.10	6.80	7.33
7-methyl	-CN	178 (dec.)	71.77	6.50	12.22	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	71.65	6.27	12.54
9-methoxy	-COOC ₂ H ₅	231 (dec.)	66.87	6.32	7.19	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	66.33	6.53	7.03
9-methoxy	-COCH ₃	216 (dec.)	68.28	6.20	7.50	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	68.50	6.52	7.61
9-ethoxy	-COOC ₂ H ₅	188 (dec.)	67.19	6.46	7.54	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅	67.00	6.80	6.80

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